

Title: Good Change Never Come Again. So Don't Waste your Valuable Time and Money here and there.

Name:Christine A. Walker

Affiliation:BTech at New York University

INTRODUCTION:

What is ILCoin?

ILCoin (ILC) is a new and superhit kind of (**cryptocurrency**) digital currency (as like Bitcoin) with cryptographic keys that is decentralized to a network of computers used by users and miners around the world and is not controlled by a single organization or government. It is another digital cryptocurrency that has gained the public's attention and is accepted by a growing number of merchants. Like other currencies, users can use the digital currency to buy goods and services online as well as in some physical stores that accept it as a form of payment. Currency traders can also trade **ILCoin** in **Ilgamos** open exchange

#ILCoin Value is increasing Day by Day..... It's Time to Save **#ILCoin**... Because ILCOIN is Next No.-1 Crypto Currency like Bitcoin We Hope immediately we will see 1 ILCoin =\$100 to \$4000 like Bitcoin **#Bitcoin** working 87 Countries but **#ILCoin** working 161 Countries About 10,000 Merchants accepted **#ILCoin** for buy sell their product at SmartAbuy in worldwide World top 6 Banks (also **#HSBC** Bank) accepted ILCoin for their digital currency.... So, we are waiting for see that Moment, 1 ILCoin=\$4000 So, Life is your & decision is your for build your life Excellent. Remember: Good Change Never Come Again. So Don't Waste your Valuable Time and Money here and there. Go to URL and read the post for Complete Details:

http://www.ilgamos.life/2017/06/how-can-you-collect-ilcoin-easy_0.html

BIOGRAPHY:

Christine A. Walker has completed his Btech at the age of 25 years from University of Boston and postdoctoral studies from University School of Medicine California, USA. He is the director of XXXX, a premier Bio-Soft service organization. He has published more than 25 papers in reputed journals and has been serving as an editorial board member of reputed.**(Up to 100 words)**